

PROFESSIONAL LEARNING COMMUNITY AND MENTORING PRACTICES AS CORRELATES OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Teachers in the school need professional assistance that would make them grow and perform better in school. There is a need to ensure the community of professionals working the school supports one another and achieves more academic accomplishment for higher school performances. With this in mind, the study is focused on the professional learning community and mentoring practices as correlates of teacher's professional development in public elementary schools in Dapdapan District- DepEd San Pablo City. The study employs the descriptive and correlational research design participated by 102 public elementary school teachers. The findings show that the Professional Learning Community Dimensions have a direct relationship with the Professional Development of the teacher-respondents. When teachers are working in a school where they can experience an established professional learning community to a very great extent this would help them be professionally developed. Moreover, professional mentoring practices were completely correlated with professional development which implies that professional mentoring is being practiced by school heads in public elementary schools this would contribute to making teachers be more developed in their profession. School Heads as suggested by the study may cultivate other styles of professional mentoring to help teachers to become more professionally developed and to enhance their other potentials in ensuring that they establish a better community of professionals in schools.

Keywords: Professionalism, professional mentoring, professional development